

ISSUES OF WIDESPREAD INTRODUCTION OF MODERN
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES TO
ADVOCACY ACTIVITIES

Kobilov Shukhrat Ruzievich

Associate Professor of the Department of Jurisprudence
of the Tashkent State Agrarian University,
Candidate of Legal Sciences

E-mail: qobilovshuhrat755@gmail.com

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Abstract: This scientific article analyzes the current problems of digitizing the institute of advocacy in Uzbekistan and its development in line with modern requirements. The author also presents his conclusions on the need to develop a mechanism for digitizing the advocacy in the process of changes in society.

Keywords: digitalization, advocacy, defender, legal representative.

Today, in our country, during the period of fundamental reforms, the institute of advocacy is increasingly entrusted with responsible and important tasks as an integral part of civil society.

In particular, the activities of advocacy institutions are gaining special importance in implementing the state's legal policy and organizing the legal literacy of citizens, increasing the legal culture of the population, and providing qualified legal assistance to citizens[1].

At the same time, the resolution sets out the goal of further developing their work in this area, as well as putting an end to excessive bureaucracy, bureaucracy, and paperlessness in the advocacy activities in the current conditions, and widely introducing digital technologies into the sector in order to establish the exchange of electronic documents with courts, law enforcement agencies, and other state bodies in its activities.

It should be emphasized that the necessary legislative framework is being formed for the successful implementation of the advocacy activities using digital technologies. At present, the process of digitizing the institutional foundations and activities of the bar in order to fully implement the reforms outlined in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026[2] and achieve the set goals does not yet adequately meet the requirements of the time. In particular, it can be said that so far only some areas have been partially introduced with digital technologies. Therefore, there is a need to ensure the systematic and consistent implementation of the tasks set in this area, and within this framework, to bring legal assistance to individuals and legal entities to a new

level by introducing information and communication technologies into the activities of the bar.

It should be noted that countries with developed information and communication technologies have achieved high development in the activities of the bar. It should be noted that the concept of introducing digital technologies into the legal profession, including various areas of activity of advocacy structures (for example, obtaining the status of an advocate, licensing, exams and advanced training, providing remote consultations, and even participating in investigative actions) is effectively applied in the experience of advanced foreign countries - such as the USA, Germany, Japan, Turkey, and Canada.

In this sense, it is necessary to fulfill the tasks of increasing the prestige of advocacy structures, eliminating bureaucratic situations that hinder the full realization of the rights and interests of citizens in obtaining legal assistance, organizing the provision of advocacy services based on digital technologies and consistently increasing their number, including improving the licensing procedures based on advanced foreign experience and modern development trends.

Accordingly, the "Legal Assistance" system was launched through the widespread introduction of digital technologies into the activities of advocacy structures and the digitization of their legal assistance services.

In addition, during the digitization process, it was determined that the issuance of licenses for the right to engage in advocacy activities would be carried out through the "License" information system.

It was also determined that state registration, re-registration and liquidation of advocacy structures would be carried out exclusively electronically, based on the "single window" principle, through the Unified Interactive Public Services Portal.

It should be noted that, unlike notary offices and notaries, work on the digitization of services provided by lawyers has not been properly organized until now.

For your information, some time ago, during the pandemic, notaries were performing their functions remotely. However, lawyers performed this task independently, without any system, in any form and form.

In order to reduce excessive legal regulation in advocacy activities, from February 1, 2023, the practice of issuing an "Electronic Advocacy Order" with a special QR code, equivalent to a traditional order issued to lawyers to conduct a specific case, was introduced by advocacy structures[3].

At the same time, the resolution stipulated that due to the introduction of digital technologies into the activities of advocacy structures, the traditional collection of statistical data from advocacy structures will be canceled and statistical data will be automatically summarized. Meanwhile, a significant change has also occurred in the process of selecting and appointing a defense attorney at state expense, which has become a headache for the inquiry officer, investigator, prosecutor, and judge. That is, now (from February 1, 2023), the recruitment of lawyers at state expense will be determined electronically, without a human factor, through random selection.

It is no secret that, despite the high demand for legal services and lawyers in general, there are sometimes justified complaints from citizens about their quality and work results. In order to prevent these situations, improve the quality of legal assistance, standardize the practice of applying law by introducing digital technologies into the system of improving the knowledge and skills of lawyers, and guarantee qualified legal assistance, a procedure is being established for organizing online advanced training for lawyers and issuing documents confirming their advanced training in electronic form.

The Ministry of Justice has also been designated as the state administration body responsible for integrating the "Legal Assistance" information system with other information and communication systems, ensuring its uninterrupted operation, ensuring information security, and ensuring the confidentiality of legal secrets. In addition, the Ministry of Justice, together with the Chamber of Advocates, is taking measures to include in the professional training and advanced training programs of lawyers by November 1, 2022 issues of improving the digital literacy and skills of lawyers, training them in information technologies and information security.

In conclusion, it should be said that the reforms underway in the field of advocacy will allow us to further increase the indicators of the introduction of modern digital technologies in the activities of advocacy structures, increase the level of ensuring the interests of citizens and organizations in obtaining qualified and high-quality legal assistance, improve the legislation and practice related to advocacy activities, and, most importantly, use effective modern digital mechanisms in implementing one of the most important tasks facing the advocacy - providing legal assistance in civil society.

References:

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